

Polarized intensity (mJy beam^{-1})

2

4

6

24 $z_{\text{ph}}=0.415$

$56^{\circ}53'00''$

$52'40''$

$20''$

$00''$

100 kpc

$16^{\text{h}}24^{\text{m}}36^{\text{s}}$

33^{s}

30^{s}

27^{s}

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

